

The Influence of Economic, Social, Vision-Mission, Political Affiliates and Candidates' Self-Image on the Trend of Selecting Candidate Head of Regional Head in East Barito District

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ABSTRACT: This research is the extent to which the influence of economic, social, vision-mission, political affiliation, and candidate's self-image on the tendency to choose a regional head candidate in the East Barito district, Central Kalimantan province with the hope that through this research, a candidate for a regional head who is qualified to develop the region both from the economic side to achieve maximum regional development. The results of this study are also expected to have implications for the development of economics, namely in the field of regional economic growth and political marketing at the district/city level. This study concludes that Economics has an insignificant and positive effect on public trust, Social has a positive and significant impact on shared beliefs, Vision-mission has a positive and significant impact on public confidence, Political affiliation has a positive and significant effect on public trust, Self-image has a positive and significant impact on public trust, Economics has a positive and significant effect on the tendency to choose candidates, Social has a positive and significant impact on the propensity to select candidates, Vision-mission has no significant impact on the direction to select candidates, Political affiliation has no significant impact on the movement to select candidates, Self-image has a positive and significant impact on the propensity to choose candidates and public trust has a positive and significant effect on the direction to choose candidates.

Keywords: Political Marketing, regional economy, General Election

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the countries in the world that uses a democratic government system, wherein this system sovereignty is entirely in the hands of the people. Democracy is a form or method of government in which all the people are involved in its implementation. The people have the right to rule, but through the representatives, they have chosen. Democracy can also be interpreted as a view that prioritizes equal rights and obligations and equal treatment for all citizens.

Democracy in the state's practice today is increasingly experiencing the peak of its development, where democracy, in a superficial sense as the government of the people, by and for the people, is so intensely engulfing every country. There has been a global trend where democracy is not only an intellectual discourse but also a political dream of various countries, especially developing countries. This requires that a State in international relations lies in its recognition of democracy.

(Polypung, 2021)said: "Etymologically, democracy comes from the Greek word "demos," which means the people, and "kratein" or "krator," which means power. So democracy means "people in power" or "government or rule by the people."One form of implementation of democracy in Indonesia is the holding of elections, namely by conducting direct elections for members of the legislature. Legislative elections are considered the most crucial elections among the people because it is the members of the legislature who will later accommodate and channel the aspirations of their people to the government. So, people must be precise in choosing candidates for legislative members.

As the election of members of the legislature, the election of the Regional Head or what is now better known as the direct election (Regional General Election) is a policy taken by the government that becomes a significant political momentum towards democratization. This momentum aligns with one of the reform goals, namely to realize a more democratic Indonesia, which can only be achieved by returning sovereignty to the people. Direct Pilkada is carried out as a concrete manifestation of the implementation of democracy by the 1945 Constitution Article 18 paragraph (4) which states that: "Governors, Regents and Mayors respectively as heads of provincial, district and city governments are elected "democratic." The meaning of democracy can have a double meaning; it can be directly elected by the people and directly elected by members of the legislature as people's representatives. According to (Prihatmoko, 2008), direct Pilkada is a democratic mechanism in the context of the recruitment of regional leaders, where the people as a whole have the right and freedom to choose the candidates they support, and candidates compete on a playing field with the same rules of the game. The result of the Pilkada is the appearance of a public official who the people own without distinguishing from where he came from and the origin of his existence because he has been placed as a protector for the people. Whoever wins the battle in the Pilkada is designated as a Regional Head (local executive) who has the legal authority of power (apparent territorial control), owns local income, and distributes them for people's welfare (having regional income be allocated for the interest of the population), and local representative balance power for controlling local executive (people's representative institution as controller of the regional executive).

Along with the development of the times and the demands of work for everyone, positions in the legislative and regional head seats are certainly a bone of contention in every election and provincial election in all regions in Indonesia, and this is no exception in East Barito Regency, Central Kalimantan Province. East Barito Regency itself is a division of South Barito Regency. East Barito Regency was established in 2002 based on Law Number 5 of 2002 concerning the Establishment of Katingan Regency, Seruyan Regency, Sukamara Regency, Lamandau Regency, Gunung Mas Regency, Pulang Pisau Regency, Murung Raya Regency, and East Barito Regency in Central Kalimantan Province. And during the period from 2002 to 2020, East Barito Regency has experienced several regional heads and legislative members changes.

Every candidate for regional head running in the Pilkada in East Barito Regency has implemented a strategy that includes economic, social, vision and mission aspects, political affiliation, and candidate *self-image*. Theoretically, applying these various aspects is believed to affect the victory of regional head candidates. This is evidenced by multiple previous research results on the various elements referred to.

For example, economic factors affect the victory in the nomination of regional heads; as evidenced by the results of research from (Ananda & Valentina, 2021) with the title Political Capital and Social Capital Athari Gauthi Ardi In the 2019 Legislative Election Victory in West Sumatra Province, it was concluded that Athari Gauthi Ardi's victory was primarily determined by the political capital owned by the person concerned, namely in the form of considerable economic prosperity (funding support) for political purposes. from his parents.

Social factors also turned out to be very influential in the nomination of regional heads; this is evidenced by the study results (Solihah, 2017) entitled Social Capital of Jeje-Adang in the 2015 Regional Head Election Pangandaran Regency. From this research, it can be concluded that public trust in Jeje-Adang is due to physical, social, and emotional closeness built several years earlier. This trust became Jeje-Adang's social capital in the Pangandaran Regency election, which became one of the reasons for the promotion and support of Jeje-Adang by the major political parties in Pangandaran (which influenced the acquisition of political capital), and which became a factor that influenced the pair's victory in the election. Pangandaran Regency election in 2015.

In addition to economic and social factors, the vision and mission of the candidates also influence the success of the regional elections. As the results of research (Asmuriyono, 2013) entitled Election of Visionary Regional Head Leadership in the City of Surabaya, it was concluded that the function of supporting resources in the election of regional head leadership was able to keep the success of regional head candidates was strongly influenced by the level of public trust, the quality of regional head candidates. And the personality of the candidate for the regional head. These three aspects are supporting factors in selecting a candidate for the regional director.

Political affiliation also affects the success of the nomination of regional heads as research results (Judge, 2015) and (Soetjipto, 1995) concluded that values play a role when individuals decide which party to support. The new party is the alternative chosen mainly by individuals who have decreased trust in the old parties (Belanger and Nadeu, 2005). These individuals then look for a new party that aligns with their values.

Based on the results of the study (Saputra et al., 2020) concluded that Political Affiliation in the 2017 Pilkada in Nagan Raya was influenced by factors: (1) Economic factors or rational choices, (2) Ideological factors/ political parties, and (3) Factors individuals as agents or actors. In the 2017 Pilkada, the Javanese in Kuala Trang Village generally supported the couple from the Aceh Party because they saw that this pair could lead Nagan Raya in the next five years,

and this pair was close to the community. This can be seen from the candidate for regent who cares about the Javanese in Kuala Trang and provides employment opportunities for them.

In contrast to the research results (Nawafi, 2018), some factors influence the political considerations of students in determining their political choices. This can be proven by sociological factors, rational choice factors, structural factors, and psychological factors that students consider in deciding their political decisions in the 2013 East Java Regional Election.

The candidate's self-image is one of the determining factors for success in the local election, as the results of research (Yahono, 2014) concluded that the imaging strategy of the candidate could not be separated from the critical role of the success team. The success team in this research carried out its role and function as a political *Public Relations (PR) in formulating an imaging strategy.*

The candidates for regional heads are very aware of the importance of public trust for the success of their candidacy. Based on the phenomenon that has developed in society so far, if a candidate for the regional head does not have public trust, it is inevitable that it will be tough for him to win the election. The research results (Pujianto & Sri Gunarsih, 2014) concluded that the public's trust in the legislative candidates in the 2014 elections they chose was relatively high. That trust is based on responsibility, has a lead character, has good ethics, and has good abilities and education. The obstacles faced by the community in giving their trust are the lack of socialization and information about legislative candidates during the 2014 election.

(Yuliono, 2013) In his research, it was concluded that the level of trust of the people of Surabaya towards political parties is relatively low; this is reflected in the increasing tendency of people who do not use their right to vote in the election of candidates for regional heads at the provincial and city levels. Inhibiting resources that affect the high number of people not exercising their right to vote in regional head elections at the local and city levels are influenced by the high level of corruption of political, socio-economic actors, political system factors, low public trust in political parties, and public apathy towards political parties – election of regional heads at the provincial and city levels.

(Rafinda & Nurmina, 2019) his research shows that novice voters have a high level of trust in the government. In other words, there is a very significant positive relationship between political participation and social confidence. The lower the social trust, the lower the level of political participation. The higher the social trust, the higher the level of political involvement of novice voters.

As also confirmed in research (Wahyudi et al., 2013), researchers concluded that increasing political participation could increase political trust and satisfaction with democracy. Individuals with political beliefs tend to participate in every policy and political decision.

(Handaningrum & Rini, 2014) in concluding that the tendency of novice voters to sympathize with candidates from among celebrities compared to non-celebrity candidates. Therefore, all components or people who have military conscription (political) authority for novice voters to become *critical and rational voters*. This means that in making a choice, not because of popularity, ethnic similarity, and emotional closeness, but because of track record, vision and mission factors, credibility, and bureaucratic experience.

Several factors influence the voter's decision to choose a regional head candidate. From the research results (Mopeng, 2015) :

- a) The sociological approach is the most influencing factor in the model of voter behavior who chooses from a sociological perspective because voters tend to make choices based on position or occupation. The existence of a sense of responsibility toward the position received is considered a gift by one of the candidates. In addition, it also shows terms of age as a benchmark for voters and education that should be qualified in terms of leadership.
- b) The psychological approach is a factor where voters no longer see which party is the candidate's vehicle for power. Big parties, small or independent, as seen from the electorate of the candidate's figure. This is because there are many interests in a party, so voters only focus on the figure used as an idol figure.
- c) The Rational Choice Approach is the approach most often highlighted by researchers. There is a sense of disappointment with each candidate, which causes voters to vote because of the advantages and disadvantages obtained when voting.
- d) Voter behavior tends to look at the figure of a candidate for the regional head. Even if they are given goods in the form of necessities or any form, it does not affect voters.
- e) Voters who do not exercise their right to vote are generally because many of the voters in Sawangan Village work and study outside the region.

From the various research results above, it is known that these multiple factors strongly influence the tendency to choose regional head candidates. To determine how much influence each independent variable has on public trust and how much power public trust has on the propensity to select candidates (*Intention to Choose*). The regional head in East Barito Regency is necessary to research this matter. This research is expected to significantly contribute to regional

head candidates in East Barito Regency in winning the regional elections in the future. And for the people of East Barito Regency itself, it is hoped that the results of this research can be an excellent political lesson and material for consideration in deciding to choose a regional head candidate who will run for East Barito Regency in the future.

II. Formulation of the problem

Based on the background and problems described above, the Influence of Economic, Social, Vision-Mission, Political Affiliation, and Candidate *Self Image* on the Tendency to Choose Candidates (*Intention To Choose*) for Regional Heads in East Barito Regency through Public Trust In Candidates as Intervening Variables, the authors try to identify several problems to be researched and discussed, namely:

1. Does Economics Affect Public Trust in Candidates for Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
2. Does Social Affect Public Trust in Candidates for Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
3. Does the Vision-Mission Affect Public Trust in Candidates for Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
4. Does Political Affiliation Affect Public Trust in Candidates for Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
5. Does Candidate Self Image Affect Public Trust in Regional Head Candidates in East Barito Regency?
6. Does Economics Affect the Tendency to Choose Candidates for Regional Heads in East Barito Regency?
7. Does Social Affect the Tendency to Choose Candidates Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
8. Does Vision-Mission Affect the Tendency to Choose Candidates Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
9. Does Political Affiliation Affect the Tendency to Choose Candidates Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
10. Does Candidate Self Image Affect the Tendency to Choose Candidates? Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
11. Does Public Trust in Candidates Affect the Tendency to Choose Candidates Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
12. Does Public Trust in Candidates Mediate the Effect of Economics on the Tendency to Vote for Candidates Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
13. Does Public Trust in Candidates Mediate Social Effects on Tendency to Choose Candidates Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
14. Does Public Trust in Candidates Mediate the influence of Vision-Mission on the Tendency to Choose Candidates Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
15. Does Public Trust in Candidates Mediate the Effect of Political Affiliation on Tendency to Vote for Candidates Regional Head in East Barito Regency?
16. Does Public Trust in Candidates Mediate the Effect of Candidate *Self Image* on the Tendency to Choose Candidates? Regional Head in East Barito Regency?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic Variable (X1)

Economics is how humans and their groups utilize limited resources to obtain various commodities and distribute them for consumption by the community (Backhouse, 2017). According to (Haboddin, 2012), local elections' political process requires prohibitive costs. Every Pilkada requires "political funds" for the expenses of pilkada activities. Political funds can be distinguished by looking at the source and use. Judging from the start, political funds come from donations from candidate pairs and donations from sympathizers (donors) both individually and in companies. In terms of users, political funds are distinguished based on expenditure allocation into expenditures to finance routine activities of political parties and campaign expenditures.

The indicators used to measure economic variables are indicators adopted from and (Niffenegger, 1988) that is:

- a. Perception of the candidate's financial ability (personal financial support).
- b. Perception of economic support (funding from donors) to candidates.
- c. Perceptions of the use of candidate's economic capital (candidate political funds): party fees, campaign costs/economic prices/promotions (political marketing/ *political marketing*), vote-buying costs (*money politics*).
- d. Perception of the candidate's capacity to advance the regional economy.
- e. Perceptions of the candidate's ability to understand regional economic problems.
- f. Perceptions of the candidate's ability to implement regional economic development strategies.

Social Variables (X2)

Social value is one part of the theory of consumption value (TCV) which states that several values can influence consumer behavior towards a product consisting of functional values, social values, emotional values, epistemic values , and conditional values (Sheth, 2009). . Social interaction is a reciprocal relationship between

individuals and individuals, individuals with groups, and groups with groups (Soekanto, 2004). According to (Putnam, 1993), social capital is a mutual trust between community members and the community towards their leaders. Social capital is defined as social institutions that involve networks, norms, and social trust that encourage social collaboration (coordination and cooperation) for the common good. In regional elections, social capital is related to building relationships and trust owned by the candidate paired with the people who voted for him (Marijan, 2010: 91).

The indicators used to measure social variables are indicators adopted from Sheth *et al.* (1991), Muin (2006:53), Elly M Setiadi & Usman Kolip (2011), Santosa (2004:11), Dayakisni & Hudaniah (2009:119), Soekanto (2012:58), Sugiyo (2005:4), Fukuyama (1999), Marijan (2010: 91), (Bourdieu *et al.*, 2010) that is:

- a. Psychological closeness to the candidate.
- b. Social similarity (there is social interaction) with the candidate.
- c. Ideological proximity to the candidate
- d. Cultural proximity to the candidate.
- e. There is trust in the community
- f. There is a network of supportive relationships.

Variable Vision-Mission (X3)

Vision is a comprehensive statement about what the organization wants, why an organization exists, and what it believes or a picture of the organization's future. Missions are statements that define what is being / will be done or want to be achieved in the (very near) or current time (Arman, 2018) .

The indicators used to measure the vision-mission variables are indicators adopted from (Wibisono, 2013) , namely:

- a. State the ideals or wishes of the candidate in the future.
- b. Short, clear, focused, and is the *standard of excellence*.
- c. Realistic and by the candidate's competence
- d. Attractive and able to inspire commitment and enthusiasm.
- e. Easy to remember and understand by the whole community and impressive to interested parties.
- f. The level of achievement can be traced.

Political Affiliation Variable (X4)

Political affiliation is defined as the merging of two different groups whose members then merge into one (Nasution, 1962) and (Endra, 1979) also suggests that political affiliation comes from the word affiliate, which has the meaning that includes being a member. Furthermore, he defines political affiliation as a merger between two or more interest groups for a specific political goal.

The indicators used to measure the political affiliation variable are indicators adopted from (Munandar, 2003) , namely:

- a. There is friendship/closeness between candidates and political parties (including ideological, cultural, economic, and social similarities).
- b. There is acceptance/support of political parties to candidates (including moral and material authorization).
- c. There is good cooperation between candidates and political parties (e.g., a solid success team).
- d. There is good political communication (the ability to avoid conflict) between candidates and political parties.

Candidate Self Image Variable(X5)

Image is how individuals present themselves to others to form judgments or other people's conceptions of themselves. Imagery is a way of creating a personal mental image or picture of something. It can also mean a visual picture evoked by words, phrases, or sentences (Fitriadi, 2011). According to (Pietrofesa & Splete, 1975), Self-Concept includes feelings about oneself physically and psychologically about the environment. Self-image consists of all values, attitudes, and beliefs about oneself in dealing with the environment. It combines several self-perceptions that influence perceptions and behavior (Mappiare-AT & Fauzan, 2019).

indicators used to measure the candidate's self-image/ *self-image* are indicators adopted from (Umam, 2017) , namely:

- a. Integrity
- b. Affection
- c. Responsibility
- d. Confident
- e. Be patient

- f. Discipline
- g. Able to control

Variable of Public Trust in Candidates (Z)

Trust is a person's willingness to be sensitive to the actions of others based on the expectation that others will perform specific actions on people who believe in them, regardless of their ability to monitor and control them (Meyer et al., 2002). (Dasgupta, 2000) states that trust is an attitude to trust individuals and groups with a certain degree of interconnectedness.

The indicators used to measure the variable of public trust in candidates are indicators adopted from (Allen & Meyer, 1990) that is:

- a. Capabilities: Candidate Competence, Candidate Experience, Candidate Institutional Endorsement, and Candidate Ability in Science.
- b. Integrity: fairness, fulfillment, fidelity, directness, relevance, and reliability.
- c. Kindness: Attention, Empathy, Confidence, and Acceptance.

Variable Tendency to Choose Candidates/ Intention To Choose (Y)

According to (Surbakti, 1992), Voter behaviors are a voting activity by individuals closely related to decision-making activities to choose and not to vote in an election so that voters will choose or support specific candidates. While voter behavior, according to (Budiardjo et al., 1998) is the activity of a person or group of people to participate actively in political life, among others, by choosing state leaders and directly or indirectly influencing *Public Policy*. These activities include voting in general elections, attending general meetings, *engaging (Contacting)* or *(Lobbying)* with government officials or members of parliament, becoming a member of a party or one of the social movements with direct action, and so on.

The indicators used to measure the variable of the tendency to choose candidates/intention to determine are indicators adopted from the Engel-Kollat-Blackwell Consumer Behavior Model (Engel-Blackwell-Miniard Model) and (Mujani, 2007), (Liddle, 1996) and (Ambardi, 2009) in his book *Power of the People* (2012), namely:

- a. Recognition (*Problem Recognition*): Input Information (*Input*) and Processing information (*Information Processing*) so that consumers/voters have enough information to make choices.
- b. Variables that affect the decision process (*Decision Process Variables*): Individual characteristics/voters (motives/ *motives* , values/ *Evaluative Criteria* , lifestyle/ *Live style* , and personality/ *Normative Compliance and Informational Influence*) , and Social influence (there is a sense of closeness in terms of culture/ *Cultural Norms* and values/ *ideological/ Values*) .
- c. Search (*Search*) External Information in the form of an interest in politics
- d. Alternative *Evaluation*: Consumers/voters' beliefs/beliefs *towards* products/candidates that lead to the formation of voters' *Attitudes* which will eventually lead to Intentions to buy (choose a candidate).
- e. Reference group/ family (*Reference Group / Family*) or a sense of psychological closeness.
- f. Situational influence (the consumer's financial condition/voters also influence the decision-making process).

IV. METHOD

The research design is all the necessary processes in the planning and implementation of research. The research method used in this study is a survey research method. (Nugroho et al., 2021) said that "survey research is research conducted on large or small populations, but the data studied are data from samples taken from that population, so that relative events are found, and the relationship between sociological and psychological." Survey research is usually used to make generalizations.

To test the proposed hypothesis, the researcher collected data using a survey technique where the variables studied were not controlled (*ex post facto*) with the following understanding:

1. Survey research takes a sample from one population and uses a questionnaire as the primary data collection tool (Singarimbun & Effendi, 1982) and (Kamsarity, 2017) .
2. The survey is a type of descriptive research method carried out on a certain number of subject groups and research objects at the same time. Surveys are not only conducted to describe a situation but also to explain the relationship between the various variables studied from things that have many units or individuals.

V. RESULTS

The following are the results of *structural testing relationships* to test each research hypothesis based on SEM output :

Table 1. Testing Structural Relationships Between Variables

Hip.	Structural Relationship		Std. Estimate	CR	P Value	Hypothesis Decision
H ₁	Economy (X1)	→ Public Trust in Candidates (Z)	0.024	0.506	0.613 <i>ns</i>	Rejected
H ₂	Social (X2)	→ Public Trust in Candidates (Z)	0.277	5.590	0.000 *	Accepted
H ₃	Vision-Mission (X3)	→ Public Trust in Candidates (Z)	0.253	4,927	0.000 *	Accepted
H ₄	Political Affiliation (X4)	→ Public Trust in Candidates (Z)	0.173	3,448	0.000 *	Accepted
H ₅	Candidate Self Image (X5)	→ Public Trust in Candidates (Z)	0.380	7,533	0.000 *	Accepted
H ₆	Economy (X1)	→ Tendency to Choose Candidates (Y)	0.212	4,249	0.000 *	Accepted
H ₇	Social (X2)	→ Tendency to Choose Candidates (Y)	0.221	4,209	0.000 *	Accepted
H ₈	Vision-Mission (X3)	→ Tendency to Choose Candidates (Y)	0.004	0.072	0.943 <i>ns</i>	Rejected
H ₉	Political Affiliation (X4)	→ Tendency to Choose Candidates (Y)	0.055	1.090	0.276 <i>ns</i>	Rejected
H ₁₀	Candidate Self Image (X5)	→ Tendency to Choose Candidates (Y)	0.258	4,536	0.000 *	Accepted
H ₁₁	Public Trust in Candidates (Z)	→ Tendency to Choose Candidates (Y)	0.243	3,692	0.000 *	Accepted
* Significant at the 0.05 level			ns Not significant			

Based on Table 5.20 above, it can be explained as follows:

1. The results of the estimation of the economic influence parameter on public trust in candidates show an insignificant effect with a *CR value* of 0.506 (smaller than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.613 (greater than 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is only 0.024, meaning that the higher the economic support of a candidate, the less likely it is to have a tangible impact on strengthening public trust in the candidate. Thus, the first hypothesis, which states that the economy affects public confidence in candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency, cannot be accepted (H₁ is rejected).
2. The results of the estimation of social influence parameters on public trust in candidates show a significant effect with a *CR value* of 5.590 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.000 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is 0.277 (positive), meaning that the higher the social value of a candidate for the regional head, the more vital public trust in the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the second hypothesis, which states that social influence on public confidence in candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency, can be accepted (H₂ is received).
3. The results of the estimation of the influence of vision and mission parameters on public trust in candidates show a significant effect with a *CR value* of 4,927 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.000 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is 0.253 (positive), meaning that the better the vision and mission of a candidate for the regional head, the more vital public trust in the candidate for the provincial crown. Thus, the third hypothesis, which states that vision-mission affects public confidence in candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency, can be accepted (H₃ is received).
4. The parameter estimation results of the influence of political affiliation on public trust in candidates show a significant effect with a *CR value* of 3.448 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.000 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is 0.173 (positive), meaning that the stronger the affiliation of a candidate for the regional head with the political parties that carry him, the more vital public

- trust in the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the fourth hypothesis, which states that political affiliation affects public confidence in regional head candidates in East Barito Regency, is acceptable (H_4 is accepted).
5. The results of the parameter estimation of the influence of self-image on public trust in candidates show a significant effect with a *CR value* of 7.533 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.000 (smaller than 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is 0.380 (positive), meaning that the stronger the self-image of a candidate for the regional head, the more vital public trust in the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the fifth hypothesis, which states that self-image affects public confidence in candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency, can be accepted (H_5 is received).
 6. The estimation results of the economic influence parameter on the tendency to choose candidates to show a significant effect with a *CR value* of 4.249 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.000 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is 0.212 (positive), meaning that the higher the economic support of a candidate for the regional head, the higher the tendency of the community to choose the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the sixth hypothesis, which states that the economy affects the propensity to select candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency, can be accepted (H_6 is received).
 7. The results of the estimation of social influence parameters on the tendency to choose candidates to show a significant effect with a *CR value* of 4.209 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.000 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is 0.221 (positive), meaning that the higher the social values of a candidate for the regional head, the higher the tendency of the community to choose the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the seventh hypothesis, which states that social influences select a candidate for the regional head in East Barito Regency, can be accepted (H_7 is received).
 8. The estimation results of the parameter of the influence of vision and mission on the tendency to choose candidates showed an insignificant effect with a *CR value* of 0.072 (smaller than 1.96). A significance value (*p-value*) of 0.943 (greater than 5% significance level). . The resulting coefficient of influence is only 0.004, meaning that the better the vision and mission conveyed by a candidate for the regional head, has not been able to have a substantial impact on the tendency of the community to choose the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the eighth hypothesis, which states that vision and mission affect the movement to elect candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency, cannot be accepted (H_8 is rejected).
 9. The parameter estimation results of the influence of political affiliation on the tendency to choose candidates to show an insignificant effect with a *CR value* of 1.090 (smaller than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.276 (greater than 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is only 0.055, meaning that the stronger the affiliation of a candidate for the regional head with political parties has not been able to have a substantial impact on the tendency of the community to choose the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the ninth hypothesis, which states that political affiliation affects the propensity to select regional head candidates in East Barito Regency, cannot be accepted (H_9 is rejected).
 10. The results of the estimation of the influence of self-image on the tendency to choose candidates to show a significant effect with a *CR value* of 4.536 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.000 (smaller than 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is 0.258 (positive), meaning that the stronger the self-image of a candidate for the regional head, the higher the public's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the tenth hypothesis, which states that self-image affects the propensity to select a candidate for the regional head in East Barito Regency, can be accepted (H_{10} is received).
 11. The estimation results of the parameter of the influence of public trust on the tendency to choose candidates to show a significant effect with a *CR value* of 3.692 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (*p-value*) of 0.000 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting coefficient of influence is 0.243 (positive), meaning that the stronger the public trust in a candidate for the regional head, the higher the public's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional director. Thus, the eleventh hypothesis, which states that public trust affects the movement to elect candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency, is acceptable (H_{11} is accepted).

Table 2. Indirect Effect Analysis

Hip	Indirect Line	Specific Indirect Effect Test (Bias-corrected percentile method)			
		Estimate	P-value	Hypothesis Decision	Mediation Type
H ₁₂	Economy (X ₁) →Public Trust (Z) →Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.006	0.514 ^{ns}	Rejected	No mediation
H ₁₃	Social (X ₂) →Public Trust (Z) →Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.057	0.009 *	Accepted	Partial mediation
H ₁₄	Vision-Mission (X ₃) →Public Trust (Z) →Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.059	0.009 *	Accepted	Fully mediation
H ₁₅	Political Affiliation (X ₄) →Public Trust (Z) →Tendency to Vote (Y)	0.038	0.007 *	Accepted	Fully mediation
H ₁₆	Self Image (X ₅) →Public Trust (Z) →Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.071	0.012 *	Accepted	Partial mediation
* . Significant at the 0.05 level		ns Not significant			

In SEM, the indirect path significance test does not use the *Sobel Test* as in the context of regression analysis or path analysis. Still, it uses the *bias-corrected percentile method approach*, a modified *Sobel test* adapted to the SEM context. The mediation path is significant if the *probability value (p-value)* is less than 0.05. Based on Table 5.21 above, it can be explained as follows:

1. Public trust does not significantly mediate the economic effect on the tendency to elect a candidate for the regional head in East Barito Regency (**H₁₂ is rejected**). The economy was able to directly influence the direction of the community to elect candidates for regional leaders. These results indicate that a regional head candidate with great economic support and excellent ability on economic issues and regional economic development strategies will encourage people to vote for the candidate for the regional director, even though the community still does not give strong trust.
2. Public trust partially mediates social influence on the tendency to elect regional head candidates in East Barito Regency (**H₁₃ accepted**). Social activities can directly or indirectly influence the direction of the community in selecting candidates for regional heads. These results indicate that a candidate for a regional leader who has high social values will be able to encourage the public to vote for the candidate for the regional head. If public trust is also strong, the tendency to choose the candidate for the regional director will be higher.
3. Public trust fully mediates the effect of the vision and mission on the tendency to elect candidates for regional heads in the East Barito Regency (**H₁₄ accepted**). Vision and mission can influence the community's direction to elect a candidate for the regional leader only if it is mediated by public trust. These results indicate that a candidate for a regional head with a good vision and mission will increase the public's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional leader only if the regional director gains strong trust from the crowd.
4. Public trust fully mediates the influence of political affiliation on the tendency to elect regional head candidates in the East Barito Regency (**H₁₅ accepted**). Political affiliation can influence the community's direction in choosing a candidate for the regional head only if it is mediated by public trust. These results indicate that a regional head candidate who has a strong affiliation with political parties will be able to increase the public's tendency to vote for that regional head candidate only if the regional head candidate gains solid public trust.
5. Public trust partially mediates the effect of self-image on the tendency to choose a candidate for the regional head in the East Barito Regency (**H₁₆ is accepted**). Self-image turns out to be able to directly or indirectly influence people's tendency to choose candidates for regional heads. These results indicate that a candidate for a regional leader who has a strong self-image will immediately encourage the public to vote for the candidate for the regional head. If the public's confidence in him is also strong, then the tendency to choose the candidate for the regional director will be even higher.

Table 3. Analysis of Total Effect

No	Path of Influence	Total Effect Analysis		
		Total Effect	P-value	Rank
1	Economy (X ₁) Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.223	0.012 *	3
2	Social (X ₂) Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.243	0.010 *	2
3	Vision-Mission (X ₃) Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.063	0.123 ns	6
4	Political Affiliation (X ₄) Voting Tendency (Y)	0.089	0.028 *	5
5	Self Image (X ₅) → Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.270	0.007 *	1
6	Public Trust (Z) → Tendency to Choose (Y)	0.186	0.016 *	4

*. Significant at the 0.05 level ns Not significant

The results of the *comprehensive effect analysis* show that the variables consisting of economic, social, political affiliation, self-image, and public trust all have a significant effect on the tendency to choose candidates because they provide a probability value (*p-value*) of less than 0.05. Meanwhile, the total impact of vision and mission on the propensity to select candidates is not significant. The *total effect* coefficient is the sum of direct and indirect effects.

Figure 1. Total Effect on the Tendency to Choose Candidates

The *total effect* shows the real influence of the predictor variables in increasing the response (in this case, the tendency to choose a candidate for the regional head); ideally, to improve the direction of the community to select a candidate for the regional director, the success team for the candidate for the regional head can design improvement programs for all variables. Exogenous, taking into account the priority scale.

The results of the *comprehensive effect analysis* conclude that to increase the public's tendency to elect a candidate for the regional head, the priorities from the highest to the lowest are:

Sequence 1: Increase social values in candidates

Social is the primary concern because this variable, in total, has the most significant impact on the tendency of the community to elect a candidate for the regional head. Candidates for regional leaders who have psychological closeness to the community, as well as social, ideological, and cultural proximity, also gain the trust of the community with the support of various social relations networks, which will have a powerful impact on the tendency of the community to choose the candidate for the regional head.

Sequence 2: Strengthening the candidate's self-image

Self-image has the second most significant impact on people's tendency to vote for candidates for the regions. Candidates for regional heads who have a strong self-image, namely integrity, confidence, discipline, and compassion for the community, will have a powerful impact on the tendency of the community to elect the candidate for the regional head.

Sequence 3: Increase public confidence in candidates

Public trust has the third most significant impact on people's tendency to vote for candidates for the regions. A candidate for a regional head who is trusted by the public, trusted because of his abilities, believes in his integrity, and believes because of the goodness of his heart, will have a powerful impact on the tendency of the community to elect the candidate for the regional head.

Sequence 4: Strengthening economic support for candidates

The economy has the fourth-largest impact on people's tendency to vote for candidates for the regions. Candidates for regional heads who have strong financial support, both from individuals and donors, have significant political funds. Their ability to understand regional economic problems and strategies for handling them will substantially impact the tendency of people to choose candidates for regional heads.

Sequence 5: Formulating a quality vision and mission

Vision-mission has the 5th most significant impact on the tendency of the community to vote for candidates for the regions. Candidates for regional heads who have a good vision and mission (clear, focused, inspiring, realistic, easy to understand) will impact the community's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional head.

Sequence 6: Strengthening affiliation with political parties

Political affiliation has the most significant impact on people's tendency to vote for candidates for the regions. Even though it has the most minor and insignificant effect on the direction of the community in choosing a candidate for the regional head, political affiliation is still considered essential to smooth out someone bureaucratically to become a regional head. For this reason, candidates for regional authorities must establish close ties with political parties, establish solid cooperation, and establish good communication so that programs can be delivered quickly to the public.

VI. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study was to analyze the influence of economic, social, vision and mission, political affiliation, and candidate's self-image on public trust in candidates and the tendency to elect regional head candidates in East Barito Regency. Based on the results of research and discussion that have been described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The economy has no significant effect on public trust in candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency. The higher the economic support of a candidate, it has not had a real impact on increasing public confidence in the candidate. The conclusion of this study is inconsistent with the decision of Renita and Tengku's (2021) research that economic capital affects trust in the nomination of regional heads.
2. Social has a positive and significant effect on public trust in regional head candidates in East Barito Regency. The conclusion of this study is consistent with the findings of the research (2010: 91) and Solihah (2019) that the higher the social capital of a candidate for the regional head, the higher the public trust in the candidate for the regional director.
3. Vision/mission has a positive and significant impact on public trust in candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency. The conclusion of this study is consistent with the findings of research by Wibisono (2006) and Asmuriyono (2013) that the better the formulation of the vision and mission of a candidate for the regional head, the higher public trust in the candidate for the regional director.
4. Political affiliation has a positive and significant effect on public trust in regional head candidates in East Barito Regency. The conclusion of this study is consistent with the findings of Hakim and Soetjipto (2014) and Ningsih (2018) that the stronger the affiliation of a candidate for the regional head with a political party, the higher public trust in the candidate for the regional director.
5. Self-image has a positive and significant effect on public confidence in regional head candidates in East Barito Regency. The conclusions of this study are consistent with the findings of Renny and Gregoria's research (2017) that the stronger the self-image of a candidate in the public eye, the higher the public's trust in the candidate.
6. The economy has a positive and significant effect on the tendency to choose candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency. The conclusion of this study is consistent with the findings of research by Sahdan and Haboddin

- (2009) and Renita and Tengku (2021) that the higher the economic support of a candidate for the regional head, the higher the public's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional director.
7. Social has a positive and significant effect on the tendency to choose candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency. The conclusion of this study is consistent with the findings of research by Marijan (2010: 91) and Solihah (2019) that the higher the social capital of a candidate for the regional head, the higher the public's tendency to elect the candidate for the regional director.
 8. Vision and mission have no significant effect on the tendency to choose a candidate for the regional head in East Barito Regency; the better the formulation of the image and assignment of a candidate for the regional director has not yet had a tangible impact on the public's tendency to elect the candidate for the regional head. The conclusion of this study is not the same as the conclusion of Asmuriyono's (2013) research that regional head candidates' vision and mission can support the success of regional head candidates.
 9. Political affiliation has no significant effect on the tendency to choose a regional head candidate in East Barito Regency; the more robust a regional head candidate's association with a political party has not yet had a tangible impact on the public's tendency to choose the regional head candidate. The conclusion of this study is not the same as the conclusion of research by Nawafi (2013) and Ningsih (2018) that the public will support a candidate for the regional head because they see a candidate pair who has a strong affiliation with the party chosen by the people in the region.
 10. Self-image has a positive and significant effect on the tendency to choose candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency. The conclusion of this study is consistent with the findings of research by Renny and Gregoria (2017) that the stronger the self-image of a candidate for the regional head in the public eye, the higher the public's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional director.
 11. Public trust has a positive and significant effect on the tendency to choose candidates for regional heads in East Barito Regency. The conclusion of this study is consistent with Yuliono (2013), Rini (2014), Pujianto (2014), and Rafind and Nurmina (2019) that the more vital public trust in a candidate for the regional head, the higher the public's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional director.
 12. Public trust does not significantly mediate the effect of economics on the propensity to vote. A candidate for a regional head with solid economic support and excellent skills regarding financial issues and regional economic development strategies will be able to encourage people to vote for the candidate for the regional head, even though the community still does not give them confidence.
 13. Public trust partially mediates social influence on the propensity to vote. A candidate for the regional head with a high social value will be able to encourage the public to vote for the candidate for the regional director. If public trust is also strong, the tendency to vote for the candidate for the regional head will be even stronger.
 14. Public trust fully mediates the influence of the vision and mission on the tendency to vote. A candidate for a regional head who has a good idea and mission will be able to increase the public's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional leader only if the candidate regional head gains strong trust from the crowd.
 15. Public trust fully mediates the influence of political affiliation on voting tendencies. A candidate for the regional head with a strong partnership with political parties will be able to increase the public's tendency to choose the candidate for the regional leader only if the candidate regional head gains strong trust from the crowd.
 16. Public trust partially mediates the effect of self-image on the tendency to vote. A candidate for the regional head with a strong self-image will immediately encourage the public to vote for the candidate for the regional director. If public confidence in him is also strong, the tendency to vote will be even higher.

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